

The Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) is a HORIZON EUROPE project.

The aim of the project is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

The INDUSAC project designs a state-of-the-art mechanism for industry-academia collaboration that is based on human-centred design principles that enable quick project co-creation. At least 300 international co-creation projects are selected for implementation to ensure the validation of the mechanism. These micro-projects led by teams consisting of students, researchers, and company staff cover various activities to target numerous industrial sectors. They are expected to create a bridge between business and academia.

The INDUSAC project focuses on four areas:

- Circularity
- General Sustainability
- Digitalisation
- Industry 4.0

1000
companies

3000
students

300
researchers

The INDUSAC project creates a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students, and 300 researchers by project end.

The project focuses on the mechanism's two main components:

➤ **The INDUSAC platform** is to build on pre-existing Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanisms to facilitate a user-friendly co-creation process. It provides the foundation for developing solutions that clearly process the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU.

➤ **The INDUSAC methodology** aims to facilitate the creation of company, student, and researcher teams by matching industry needs with students' and researchers' interests and skills. The methodology is built on a baseline of pre-existing co-creation approaches and offers guidance packages, as well as processes and tools for its smooth functioning. It provides detailed user journey maps.

Open Calls

INDUSAC launches a continuous open call for universities. The aim is to engage with at least 15 organisations at the start of the open call and reach at least 30 by the end of it. The open call for universities and research centres will be open for 18 months, starting in September 2023. Once registered in the open call, the universities and research centres will promote participation in the competitions among their students, who will be able to express interest, join a team and submit their solutions to companies' challenges anytime during the open call. Each challenge will have a specific deadline during the open call, which will be announced two months in advance to allow a suitable reaction from the companies and students. INDUSAC will select 300 co-creation teams formed by at least three students from three different EU countries, who will receive the INDUSAC programme support grant.

The project started on 1st September 2022 and will run for three years.

Partnership

The project coordinator is Jožef Stefan Institute (Slovenia) and other partners are Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley (Poland), Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Pécs-Baranya (Hungary), Cyprus University of Technology (Cyprus), Bax & Company (Spain), UPC Technology Center (Spain), EIT Manufacturing East (Austria), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany), and Innoget (Spain).

